

Indefinite Terms in Aristotelian Logic and Their Modern Treatment

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Abstract: Building on Miller’s (1938) work, this paper employs reduced truth tables—which exclude empty terms and preserve traditional oppositional relations—to analyze logical equivalences among categorical propositions containing negated terms. It is demonstrated that: (1) every basic logical equivalence (e.g., “*A belongs to every B*” \leftrightarrow “*Non-A belongs to no B*”) generates a complementary version (“*Non-A belongs to every non-B*” \leftrightarrow “*A belongs to no non-B*”) through uniform term complementation. (2) This property of closure under complementation explains the internal consistency of Aristotle’s treatment of indefinite terms. The resulting system successfully preserves valid syllogistic modes within a broader and more unified semantic architecture.

Keywords: Aristotelian logic; categorical logic; negated terms; complementary terms; truth-value analysis; logical opposition; distribution of terms; logical dependence; syllogistic validity; Aristotelian reductions; the “Two Barbaras” problem; closure under complementation.

1. Introduction

The logical status of indefinite or negated terms—such as “*non-just*” and “*non-white*” (*On Interpretation* 10; *Prior Analytics* I.46)—remains an open question in Aristotelian studies. Their frequent exclusion from syllogistic analysis not only limits the scope of existing findings but also points to an underlying problem: the extensive literature on the subject is fragmented, lacking a consolidated analytical paradigm to integrate them.

Within this context, the systematic framework developed by Miller (1938)—building in some respects on earlier work by Keynes (1906)—is both comprehensive and robust, establishing the relations of equivalence and opposition among categorical propositions that include negated terms. Nevertheless, his unifying taxonomy has not been fully incorporated into recent lines of inquiry. Scholars such as Sommers (1970; 1982), Alvarez & Correia (2012; 2017), Parsons (2014), Alvarez-Fontecilla (2016), Radulescu (2022), García-Cruz & Demey (2023), Santos (2023), and Correia (2017; 2024) have made valuable contributions to specific problems involving negated terms. However, the particular and specialized nature of these studies has prevented Miller’s system from being fully leveraged as a common foundation.

To address this situation, the present work provides a rigorous validation of Miller’s model using reduced truth tables, while simultaneously generating new semantic

information. This information remains relevant for syntactic developments, irrespective of whether the syllogistic is interpreted as a formal axiomatic system or as a system of natural deduction (Corcoran 1994).

In contemporary logic, the notion of an “indefinite term” has been replaced by the sharper concept of a term’s complement—defined as the set of all elements not falling under the extension of the negated term. Under this interpretation, a proposition such as “*A belongs to every non-A*” is inherently inconsistent, as it requires a class and its complement to share common elements. Historically, ambiguity in negation was common in ancient logic. For Aristotle, negation applies not only to terms but also functions as a quality inherent to certain propositions (i.e., the negation of the copula). Moreover, he implicitly treats negation in a manner akin to a truth-functional operator on propositions—paralleling modern external negation.

Aristotle’s presupposition that terms are non-empty (Smith 2022: 5.2; Łukasiewicz 1957: 130; Hintikka 1973; Corcoran 1974: 104) enables the construction of reduced truth tables for categorical propositions, where truth values are determined by traditional oppositional relations. However, this approach must be expanded to incorporate indefinite terms, requiring two key postulates: (1) the complement of a term must be treated as another non-empty term, and (2) the existence of a term entails the existence of its complement, and *vice versa*. These assumptions are critical for maintaining the system’s coherence and preventing paradoxes.

It would be misleading to dismiss Aristotelian logic for excluding empty terms. Far from constituting a limitation, this characteristic facilitates connections between non-modal and modal logic. To illustrate without technical elaboration: If we hypothesize that logs “do not exist,” the indefinite proposition “*Logs are white*” acquires a modally significant value, transforming into “*It is not possible for logs to be white*” (Prior Analytics I.46; Matía Cubillo, 2024).

2. Indefinite Terms in Aristotelian Logic: A Formalization Using Reduced Truth Tables

For notation, we use uppercase letters (A, B, C) to represent terms and an overbar ($\bar{A}, \bar{B}, \bar{C}$) to denote their complements (*non-A, non-B, non-C*). Following standard practice, we use lowercase letters to classify categorical propositions: universal affirmative (a), universal negative (e), particular affirmative (i), and particular negative (o). This notation simplifies the representation of categorical propositions. For example, “*A belongs to every non-B*” (or “*All non-B are A*”) is formalized concisely as $Aa\bar{B}$.

To construct reduced truth tables, we eliminate truth-value combinations that violate Aristotle’s oppositional relations. When assigning truth values to categorical forms, we systematically exclude rows that would produce non-tautological expressions when formalizing the core logical relations. This method preserves the essential characteristics of each oppositional type:

- Contradiction relations ($AaB \leftrightarrow AoB$ and $AeB \leftrightarrow AiB$) fail if their component propositions share identical truth values.
- Subalternation relations ($AaB \rightarrow AiB$ and $AeB \rightarrow AoB$) fail only if a universal proposition is true while its corresponding particular is false.
- Contrariety ($AaB \uparrow AeB$) is violated only if both universal propositions are simultaneously true.
- Subcontrariety ($AiB \vee AoB$) yields false only when both particular propositions are false.

Table 1 captures these constraints:

Table 1. Truth Values of the Categorical Forms of Proposition AB

	<i>AaB</i>	<i>AoB</i>	<i>AeB</i>	<i>AiB</i>
1	T	F	F	T
2	F	T	F	T
3	F	T	T	F

The complete logical structure is formalized as:

$$(1) \quad (AaB \leftrightarrow AoB) \wedge (AeB \leftrightarrow AiB) \wedge (AeB \rightarrow AoB) \wedge (AaB \rightarrow AiB) \wedge (AaB \uparrow AeB) \wedge (AiB \vee AoB)$$

No truth-value assignment beyond Table 1 satisfies (1) as a tautology.

Extending this method to account for negated terms, we incorporate categorical forms for all complementary term pairs, including *BA*, $\bar{A}\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}\bar{A}$, $A\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}A$, $\bar{A}B$, and $B\bar{A}$, while ensuring all relations of opposition remain logically consistent. After eliminating rows that are incompatible with the principles of Aristotelian logic, we derive Table 2:

Table 2. Reduced Truth Table for Categorical Forms of Propositions *AB*, *BA*, $\bar{A}\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}\bar{A}$, $A\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}A$, $\bar{A}B$, and $B\bar{A}$

	$\bar{A}eB$	$\bar{A}iB$	$\bar{A}aB$	$\bar{A}oB$	$Ae\bar{B}$	$Ai\bar{B}$	$Aa\bar{B}$	$Ao\bar{B}$	$\bar{B}eA$	$\bar{B}iA$	$\bar{B}aA$	$\bar{B}oA$	$Be\bar{A}$	$Bi\bar{A}$	$Ba\bar{A}$	$Bo\bar{A}$
	<i>AaB</i>	<i>AoB</i>	<i>AeB</i>	<i>AiB</i>	$\bar{A}a\bar{B}$	$\bar{A}o\bar{B}$	$\bar{A}e\bar{B}$	$\bar{A}i\bar{B}$	<i>BaA</i>	<i>BoA</i>	<i>BeA</i>	<i>BiA</i>	$\bar{B}a\bar{A}$	$\bar{B}o\bar{A}$	$\bar{B}e\bar{A}$	$\bar{B}i\bar{A}$
1	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T
2	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T
3	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T
4	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T
5	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F
6	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T
7	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F

Readers can independently verify these results using Venn diagrams (Grennan 1985), under the assumption that neither the terms nor their complements are empty. To prevent an unnecessary expansion of the table, we have incorporated the equivalences between the categorical forms of propositions *AB* and $\bar{A}\bar{B}$, $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ and $A\bar{B}$, *BA* and $\bar{B}\bar{A}$, and $B\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}\bar{A}$, all of which are self-evident. Some columns produce identical outputs. The table can be simplified to only eight columns, immediately reflecting the equivalences. However, we have chosen to present Table 2 in this format for intuitive clarity.

Table 2, appropriately simplified to eight columns, makes it possible to represent the relationships between categorical propositions using logical connectives, thereby providing a straightforward reproduction of the complete information found in Miller's Table of Opposition (1938: 47; cf. Keynes 1906: 142–143). Below is an excerpt of these relationships, using *AB* and $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ as canonical representatives:

$$AaB \leftrightarrow AaB, AaB \leftrightarrow AoB, AaB \uparrow AeB, AaB \rightarrow AiB, AaB \top \bar{A}a\bar{B}, AaB \top \bar{A}o\bar{B}, AaB \uparrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, AaB \rightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$AoB \leftrightarrow AaB, AoB \leftrightarrow AoB, AoB \leftarrow AeB, AoB \vee AiB, AoB \top \bar{A}a\bar{B}, AoB \top \bar{A}o\bar{B}, AoB \leftarrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, AoB \vee \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$AeB \uparrow AaB, AeB \rightarrow AoB, AeB \leftrightarrow AeB, AeB \leftrightarrow AiB, AeB \uparrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, AeB \rightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}, AeB \top \bar{A}e\bar{B}, AeB \top \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$AiB \leftarrow AaB, AiB \vee AoB, AiB \leftrightarrow AeB, AiB \leftrightarrow AiB, AiB \leftarrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, AiB \vee \bar{A}o\bar{B}, AiB \top \bar{A}e\bar{B}, AiB \top \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$\bar{A}a\bar{B} \top AaB, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \top AoB, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \uparrow AeB, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow AiB, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \uparrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$\bar{A}o\bar{B} \top AaB, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \top AoB, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftarrow AeB, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \vee AiB, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftarrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, \bar{A}o\bar{B} \vee \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$\bar{A}e\bar{B} \uparrow AaB, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow AoB, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \top AeB, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \top AiB, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \uparrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$\bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftarrow AaB, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \vee AoB, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \top AeB, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \top AiB, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftarrow \bar{A}a\bar{B}, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \vee \bar{A}o\bar{B}, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}, \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

Here, \top is defined as the constant truth connective, which always returns *true* regardless of the truth values of its operands.

This formalization also enables the construction of complex formulas such as (1) and facilitates determining whether they are tautologies, contradictions, or contingent statements within Aristotelian logic.

3. Traditional Oppositional Relations and Immediate Transformations

The analysis of truth-value combinations using reduced truth tables allows for the use of standard logical connectives, facilitating a systematic and intuitive establishment of the relations of contradiction, contrariety, subcontrariety, and subalternation. To simplify the examination, we will consider only the forms AB and $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ as canonical representatives, as the remaining variants can be derived through logical equivalences.

The following relations are obtained from Table 2:

Contrariety

 $AaB \uparrow AeB$
 $AaB \uparrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}$
 $\bar{A}a\bar{B} \uparrow AeB$
 $\bar{A}a\bar{B} \uparrow \bar{A}e\bar{B}$

Subcontrariety

$$AiB \vee AoB \qquad AiB \vee \bar{A}o\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}i\bar{B} \vee AoB \qquad \bar{A}i\bar{B} \vee \bar{A}o\bar{B}$$

Contradiction

$$AaB \leftrightarrow AoB \qquad AeB \leftrightarrow AiB \qquad \bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

Subalternation

$$AaB \rightarrow AiB \qquad AaB \rightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow AiB \qquad \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}$$

$$AeB \rightarrow AoB \qquad AeB \rightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow AoB \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}$$

All these relations are tautological within the Aristotelian system. The methodology employed provides a comprehensive analysis of the logical connections. Under the assumption of non-empty terms, the reduced truth tables guarantee that no other combinations consistent with the system exist. Thus, while remaining faithful to the original texts, the method generates all valid relations.

In an analogous manner, the effect of negated terms on immediate inferences (conversion, obversion, and contraposition) can be examined systematically. These inferences can be derived more simply than in Miller (1938: 72–73) by using Table 2, thereby eliminating the need for distribution rules and providing precise information about the most appropriate logical connective for each relation.

We again simplify the analysis by taking the categorical forms AB and $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ as canonical representatives:

Conversion (exchange of terms):

$$AeB \leftrightarrow BeA \qquad AiB \leftrightarrow BiA \qquad AaB \rightarrow BiA \qquad AeB \rightarrow BoA$$

$$\bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{B}e\bar{A} \qquad \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{B}i\bar{A} \qquad \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{B}i\bar{A} \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow \bar{B}o\bar{A}$$

Obversion (change of quality and negation of the predicate)

$$AaB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}eB \qquad AeB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}aB \qquad AiB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}oB \qquad AoB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}iB$$

$$\bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ae\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Aa\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ao\bar{B} \qquad \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ai\bar{B}$$

Contraposition (negation and exchange of terms)

$$AaB \leftrightarrow \bar{B}a\bar{A} \qquad AoB \leftrightarrow \bar{B}o\bar{A} \qquad \bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow BaA \qquad \bar{A}o\bar{B} \leftrightarrow BoA$$

$$AeB \top \bar{B}e\bar{A} \qquad AiB \top \bar{B}i\bar{A} \qquad \bar{A}e\bar{B} \top BeA \qquad \bar{A}i\bar{B} \top BiA$$

4. Basic Logical Equivalences and Closure Under Complementation

The reduced truth table method systematizes the analysis of logical relations and valid transformations in Aristotelian logic. Using Table 2—which exhaustively lists all valid

combinations under Aristotelian assumptions (non-emptiness, opposition relations)—we can identify all logical equivalences among categorical propositional forms, thereby resolving ambiguities in the use of negated terms.

These relations are grouped into logical equivalence classes, where any proposition can be validly transformed into another within its group:

1. $AaB, \bar{A}eB, \bar{B}a\bar{A}, Be\bar{A}, \neg(\bar{A}iB), \neg(AoB), \neg(\bar{B}o\bar{A}),$ and $\neg(Bi\bar{A})$
2. $AeB, \bar{A}aB, \bar{B}aA, BeA, \neg(\bar{A}oB), \neg(AiB), \neg(\bar{B}oA),$ and $\neg(BiA)$
3. $AiB, \bar{A}oB, \bar{B}oA, BiA, \neg(\bar{A}aB), \neg(AeB), \neg(\bar{B}aA),$ and $\neg(BeA)$
4. $AoB, \bar{A}iB, \bar{B}o\bar{A}, Bi\bar{A}, \neg(\bar{A}eB), \neg(AaB), \neg(\bar{B}a\bar{A}),$ and $\neg(Be\bar{A})$
5. $\bar{A}a\bar{B}, Ae\bar{B}, \bar{B}eA, BaA, \neg(Ai\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{A}o\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{B}iA),$ and $\neg(BoA)$
6. $\bar{A}e\bar{B}, Aa\bar{B}, \bar{B}e\bar{A}, Ba\bar{A}, \neg(Ao\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{A}i\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{B}i\bar{A}),$ and $\neg(Bo\bar{A})$
7. $\bar{A}i\bar{B}, Ao\bar{B}, \bar{B}i\bar{A}, Bo\bar{A}, \neg(Aa\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{A}e\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{B}e\bar{A}),$ and $\neg(Ba\bar{A})$
8. $\bar{A}o\bar{B}, Ai\bar{B}, \bar{B}iA, BoA, \neg(Ae\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{A}a\bar{B}), \neg(\bar{B}eA),$ and $\neg(BaA)$

Each line represents a complete class of logical equivalence within the system, enabling the reduction of any analysis to canonical representatives. This structure precisely matches Miller's Table of Propositional Forms (1938: 37–38; cf. Keynes 1906: 141).

The full inventory of logical equivalences demonstrates that Aristotelian logic is closed under complementation. For every basic logical equivalence (e.g., $AaB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}eB$), there exists a complementary version ($\bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ae\bar{B}$) obtained by uniformly replacing each term with its complement. This pattern holds consistently:

$$AiB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}oB \text{ and } \bar{A}i\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ao\bar{B},$$

$$AeB \leftrightarrow BeA \text{ and } \bar{A}e\bar{B} \leftrightarrow \bar{B}e\bar{A} \dots$$

A thorough examination of Table 2 confirms that there are no exceptions—all valid combinations adhere to this symmetry. Aristotle implicitly assumes double complementation ($\bar{\bar{A}} \equiv A$, Miller 1938: 31, 36–38), though he does not formalize it as an explicit rule.

This closure under complementation ensures the system's coherence in its handling of indefinite terms without the need for any additional axioms.

In the *Prior Analytics*, when Aristotle examines the relationship between premises and conclusion in terms of truth and falsity, his method can be understood as a conceptual precursor to exhaustive case verification. Our use of reduced truth tables as a demonstrative tool—while technically anachronistic in its modern formulation—aligns with Aristotle's practice of examining all relevant possibilities to guarantee syllogistic validity (Camacho 2008: 140). This does not preclude the search for methodological principles to systematize deductive analysis.

The admission of all four truth-value combinations (TT, TF, FT, FF) is a necessary condition for the logical independence of two categorical propositions (see, e.g., Baker 1977: 165–166). The absence of any one of these combinations immediately indicates a logical dependence. Reduced truth tables provide a method for studying the relationships

between categorical propositions. Although syllogistic validity has traditionally been based on properties of the propositions themselves, such as term distribution, it can also be analyzed through the underlying logical dependencies relations that support it.

The systematization of valid syllogisms that include negated terms is a task Aristotle does not appear to have addressed. When applying the reduced truth table method, the fundamental principle remains the same: the logical dependence between the conjunction of the premises and the conclusion is based exclusively on the presence of the TT, FT, and FF truth-value combinations and the absence of the TF combination (Matía Cubillo 2025). Of course, the relationships of opposition in all directly or indirectly involved categorical propositions must be rigorously observed. These conditions determine the differentiation of the three Aristotelian figures and enable the transformation of valid modes between figures (cf. Miller 1938: 48, 80–81; Alvarez & Correia 2012; Correia 2017; Radulescu 2022).

5. Syllogistic Transformations and Validity via Reduced Truth Tables

In his syllogistic figures, Aristotle does not employ a rigid alphabetical notation—unlike the Scholastics—but rather represents terms (predicate, middle, and subject) according to their contextual role. Modern translations of *Prior Analytics* I.4–6 use Latinized letters to designate terms in each figure: *A*, *B*, and *C* for the first figure; *M*, *N*, and *X* for the second; and *P*, *S*, and *R* for the third. We consciously depart from the medieval Scholastic practice of fixed letter schemes with strict distribution rules.

Our modern formalization treats the differences between syllogistic figures as variations in proposition ordering. Taking the first figure’s standard *AB–BC–AC* form as baseline, the second figure results from swapping the minor premise and conclusion (yielding *AB–AC–BC*), while the third figure emerges from exchanging the major premise and conclusion (producing *AC–BC–AB*). This proposition-reordering approach has been adopted in some recent formal treatments of Aristotelian logic (e.g., Smith 2022: 5.1; Koutsoukou-Argyraiki & Wapniarski 2025: Table 3).

Medieval logicians took a fundamentally different approach, distinguishing figures by the middle term’s syntactic position (subject or predicate) in each premise rather than proposition rearrangement. They derived the second figure by modifying the major premise (*BA–BC–AC*) and the third figure by altering the minor premise (*AB–CB–AC*), viewing these as substantive changes to premise form rather than simple positional adjustments.

Our notation preserves key Aristotelian features: predicate-first ordering, subject-second position, and consistent middle term placement. This approach prioritizes logical dependency relations over mere grammatical positions, providing analytical tools to understand syllogistic structures while remaining faithful to Aristotle’s original conception. Furthermore, our model preserves the logical dependencies among propositions across all three figures while eliminating reliance on the medieval concept of term distribution—the technical analysis of when a term refers to its entire extension within a proposition, complete with systematic identification rules. This concept is not explicitly formulated in Aristotle’s works; it represents a later Scholastic development. Aristotle does not base his syllogistic on this notion; rather, his analysis focuses on the logical necessity of the conclusion.

It is particularly revealing how the substitution of logically equivalent propositions with negated terms enables the re-expression of a syllogism in what appear to be different modes or figures. Take for instance the first-figure Barbara syllogism:

$$(AaB \wedge BaC) \rightarrow AaC$$

This same logical structure can be represented as a first-figure Celarent:

$$(\bar{A}eB \wedge BaC) \rightarrow \bar{A}eC$$

as a second-figure Camestres:

$$(\bar{B}a\bar{A} \wedge \bar{B}eC) \rightarrow \bar{A}eC$$

or as a second-figure Cesare:

$$(Be\bar{A} \wedge BaC) \rightarrow \bar{A}eC$$

The fundamental syllogism remains unchanged—we are merely observing the same logical bones dressed in different notational clothing. In the following reduced truth table—adapted to the three original Aristotelian figures—it can be verified that we are examining the exact same columns for the premises and the conclusion:

Table 3. Reduced Truth Table for Aristotle's Three Original Syllogistic Figures

	$\bar{B}a\bar{A}$	$\bar{B}o\bar{A}$	$\bar{B}aA$	$\bar{B}oA$	$\bar{C}a\bar{B}$	$\bar{C}o\bar{B}$	$\bar{C}aB$	$\bar{C}oB$	$\bar{C}a\bar{A}$	$\bar{C}o\bar{A}$	$\bar{C}aA$	$\bar{C}oA$
	$Be\bar{A}$	$Bi\bar{A}$	BeA	BiA	$Ce\bar{B}$	$Ci\bar{B}$	CeB	CiB	$Ce\bar{A}$	$Ci\bar{A}$	CeA	CiA
	$\bar{A}eB$	$\bar{A}iB$	$\bar{A}aB$	$\bar{A}oB$	$\bar{B}eC$	$\bar{B}iC$	$\bar{B}aC$	$\bar{B}oC$	$\bar{A}eC$	$\bar{A}iC$	$\bar{A}aC$	$\bar{A}oC$
	AaB	AoB	AeB	AiB	BaC	BoC	BeC	BiC	AaC	AoC	AeC	AiC
1	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T
2	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T
3	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T
4	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T
5	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T
6	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
7	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T
8	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T
9	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F
10	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T
11	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T
12	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F
13	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T
14	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T
15	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
16	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F
17	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T
18	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T	F	T	T	F
19	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T
20	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	F	T
21	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F

In all four formulas considered, whenever the antecedent is true, the conclusion must also be true. This occurs precisely in row 1 in every case.

Table 3 provides a semantic validation of Aristotelian reductions, including indirect proof. Aristotle employs this method, for instance, with the Baroco syllogism of the second figure, which has the form:

$$(AaB \wedge AoC) \rightarrow BoC$$

The procedure for the indirect proof is as follows: by denying the conclusion (asserting BaC instead of BoC) and combining it with the major premise (AaB), we can use the Barbara syllogism to derive the negation of the original minor premise:

$$(AaB \wedge BaC) \rightarrow AaC$$

Since this result (AaC) directly contradicts the original minor premise (AoC), the validity of the original conclusion (BoC) is demonstrated by contradiction.

Without resorting to this indirect proof, Table 3 allows for the verification of Baroco's validity: in every row where the antecedent ($AaB \wedge AoC$) is true (rows 3, 5, and 6), the consequent (BoC) is also true.

Aristotle uses an analogous procedure for the Bocardo syllogism of the third figure:

$$(AoC \wedge BaC) \rightarrow AoB$$

Here, the negation of the conclusion, when combined with the minor premise, leads via Barbara to the negation of the original major premise:

$$(AaB \wedge BaC) \rightarrow AaC$$

The contradiction that arises from denying the conclusion proves that the original Bocardo syllogism is valid.

Again, Table 3 provides direct semantic evidence for the validity of Bocardo: in every instance where its antecedent ($AoC \wedge BaC$) holds true (rows 8, 9, and 16), the consequent (AoB) is also true. As a corollary, this shows that if AaC and BoC are both false, AaB must also be false.

However, the incorporation of negated terms—by leveraging equivalences between categorical propositions—allows us to rewrite the Baroco and Bocardo modes into the first figure without resorting to indirect proof.

Consider the Baroco syllogism:

$$(AaB \wedge AoC) \rightarrow BoC$$

This can be transformed into a first-figure Darii syllogism:

$$(\bar{B}a\bar{A} \wedge \bar{A}iC) \rightarrow \bar{B}iC$$

as well as into a first-figure Ferio syllogism:

$$(Be\bar{A} \wedge \bar{A}iC) \rightarrow BoC$$

and, by exchanging the order of the premises, into Bocardo:

$$(\bar{C}o\bar{A} \wedge \bar{B}a\bar{A}) \rightarrow \bar{C}o\bar{B}$$

Valid syllogisms that contain a particular premise can be rewritten using similar procedures, thereby facilitating their reduction to the first figure. Nevertheless, indirect proof remains necessary to establish their ultimate dependence on a universal deductive mode like Barbara. This is also the case for the Darapti and Felapton modes, which

conclude with particular propositions. The extension of indirect proof to all traditional valid modes is detailed in Wapniarski & Urbański (2024).

A remaining task is to expand the Table 3 to include previously unconsidered equivalence classes with negated terms, as well as to analyze the logical dependency relations they generate.

6. Maintaining Syllogistic Validity within an Expanded Semantic Framework

To properly discuss logical independence between categorical propositions, it is necessary to establish stricter conditions than merely the presence of all four truth-value combinations. As shown in Table 1, the semantic definition of a categorical proposition is determined by its truth value across three mutually exclusive scenarios: holding in all cases, failing in all cases, and holding in some cases but not in others. If a truth value cannot be assigned to a proposition in any one of these three scenarios, it is because the proposition is logically incongruent with the truth values of another proposition under consideration—a conflict that violates the established relations of opposition.

Accounting for this limitation, two categorical propositions are logically independent if and only if the three scenarios that define each one individually are compatible in every possible combination when they are considered jointly. This requires a truth table with nine non-equivalent rows to affirm, in a strong sense, that two categorical propositions are logically independent. We must ensure that the two propositions are compatible across all semantic scenarios.

Under this more restrictive and robust condition, the categorical forms of propositions AB and $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ (and consequently, the forms of $\bar{A}B$, $A\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}A$, $B\bar{A}$, and BA , for which they serve as canonical representatives) are not logically independent. When the categorical forms of AB are considered in a syllogism, the categorical forms of $\bar{A}\bar{B}$ are also inherently involved in the reasoning, despite constituting distinct equivalence classes. As the truth values in Table 2 demonstrate, they are intertwined through tautological relations such as:

$$AaB \rightarrow \bar{A}i\bar{B}, AeB \rightarrow \bar{A}o\bar{B}, \bar{A}a\bar{B} \rightarrow AiB, \bar{A}e\bar{B} \rightarrow AoB, \dots$$

The Aristotelian system of categorical forms, when expanded to include complementary terms, forms a coherent and densely interconnected network of logical relations. In this system, asserting something about a class necessarily implies something about its complement and its relationship to other classes.

Expanding Table 3 to include the equivalence classes for $\bar{A}\bar{B}$, $\bar{B}\bar{C}$, and $\bar{A}\bar{C}$ shows that the valid syllogistic modes are preserved. This expansion provides greater semantic definition, offering a broader understanding of the subclasses formed by their truth-value intersections. Ultimately, incorporating complementary terms allows the model to achieve a richer description of the universe of discourse.

In the case of the Barbara mode, for example, it is possible to establish various restrictive conditions that, while preserving syllogistic validity, yield complete semantic definitions (when using Venn diagrams, they account for information in every resulting sector):

1. $(AaB (\wedge \bar{A}a\bar{B}) \wedge BaC (\wedge \bar{B}a\bar{C})) \rightarrow AaC (\wedge \bar{A}a\bar{C})$
2. $(AaB (\wedge \bar{A}a\bar{B}) \wedge BaC (\wedge \bar{B}o\bar{C} \wedge \bar{B}i\bar{C})) \rightarrow AaC (\wedge \bar{A}o\bar{C} \wedge \bar{A}i\bar{C})$

$$3. (AaB (\wedge \bar{A}o\bar{B} \wedge \bar{A}i\bar{B}) \wedge BaC (\wedge \bar{B}a\bar{C})) \rightarrow AaC (\wedge \bar{A}o\bar{C} \wedge \bar{A}i\bar{C})$$

$$4. (AaB (\wedge \bar{A}o\bar{B} \wedge \bar{A}i\bar{B}) \wedge BaC (\wedge \bar{B}o\bar{C} \wedge \bar{B}i\bar{C})) \rightarrow AaC (\wedge \bar{A}o\bar{C} \wedge \bar{A}i\bar{C})$$

This stronger criterion of logical independence between propositions is useful in various contexts within Aristotelian logic. It allows for a reconsideration of problems such as that of the “Two Barbaras” (Łukasiewicz 1957: 183–191; McCall 1963). Furthermore, despite doubts raised since antiquity (Mueller 1999; Fortenbaugh 1999; Huby 2002; Gili 2012), this analysis shows that there is in fact no error in the passage from *Prior Analytics* I.9, 30a24–28.

A brief *excursus* for those familiar with the problem: In the *Barbara* mode, a necessary major premise— $N(AaB)$, which encompasses all cases where it is true (rows 1–6 in Table 3)—allows for a true conclusion to be deduced regardless of the truth values of the minor premise. It is irrelevant whether BaC is true, false because it holds only in some cases, or false because it does not hold in any case. In any of these three situations, AaC can still be true (rows 1, 2, and 4 of Table 3). Since the truth of the conclusion depends logically only on the major premise, it must be affirmed to be as necessary as the latter:

$$(N(AaB) \wedge BaC) \rightarrow N(AaC)$$

Conversely, when the minor premise is necessary— $N(BaC)$, which encompasses all cases where it is true (rows 1, 7–9, and 16 in Table 3)—the truth of the conclusion maintains its logical dependence on the major premise. AaC can only be true if AaB is either true or false because it holds only in some cases (that is, the possibility that AaB is false because it does not hold in any case is excluded). For this reason, the conclusion is assertoric, not necessary:

$$(AaB \wedge N(BaC)) \rightarrow AaC$$

7. Oppositional Relations and Negated Terms in *Prior Analytics* I.46

Closure under complementation explains the internal coherence of Aristotle’s treatment of negated terms. *Prior Analytics* I.46 proves particularly significant here, where Aristotle systematically develops the logical relationships for propositions containing negated terms. Having rigorously demonstrated that “*not to be this*” neither equals “*to be non-this*” nor constitutes its logical negation, he then establishes the governing rules of opposition:

Let A stand for ‘to be good,’ B stand for ‘not to be good,’ C stand for ‘to be not good’ (which is below B), and D stand for ‘not to be not good’ (which is below A). Now, either A or B will belong to everything but not <both> to any same thing [$AA \leftrightarrow BB$]; and also either C or D will belong to everything, but not < both > to any same thing [$CC \leftrightarrow DD$]. And it is necessary for B to belong to everything to which C belongs: for if it is true to say that something is not-white, then it is true to say that it is not white (for it is impossible to be white and to be not-white at the same time, or to be a not-white log and to be a white log), so that if the affirmation does not belong then the denial will. But C does not always belong to B (for what is not a log at all will not be a not-white log) [$CC \rightarrow BB$]. Therefore, in reverse order, D belongs to everything to which A belongs: for either C or D belongs to everything, and since it is not possible to be at once not-white and white, D will belong to A (for of that which is white it is true to say that it is not not-white). But A will not be true of every D (for it is not true to say A—that it is a white log—of what is not a log at all;

consequently, it is true to say D, but it is not true to say A, i.e., that it is a white log) [$AA \rightarrow DD$]. It is also clear that A and C cannot belong to anything the same [$AA \uparrow CC$], and that B and D can belong to the same thing [$BB \vee DD$]. (51b36–52a13, Smith translation 1989)

To avoid confusion with Aristotelian notation, we use doubled uppercase letters (AA , BB , CC , DD) for propositions. The corresponding logical relations, as formalized in square brackets within the text, follow the same convention.

Aristotle’s analysis examines truth-value combinations in a manner functionally analogous to reduced truth tables. Instead of modern notation, he arranges metalinguistic letters into columns of contradictory propositions, constructing what became traditional square of opposition:

AA (<i>to be good</i>)	BB (<i>not to be good</i>)
DD (<i>not to be non-good</i>)	CC (<i>to be non-good</i>)

Throughout the passage, Aristotle shows which truth-value combinations the propositions can simultaneously adopt, according to the logical constraints established in the text. He carefully adapts his examples to illustrate each intended pattern. His analysis reveals three possible configurations:

1. ^a	T	F	2. ^a	F	T	3. ^a	F	T
	T	F		T	F		F	T

The possibility of the second configuration proves that BB and CC are not identical: “*not to be this*” does not equate to “*to be non-this*.” Similarly, the first and third configurations establish they are not contradictories either: “*not to be this*” does not constitute the logical negation of “*to be non-this*.”

Aristotle places particular emphasis on what he terms “not possible” combinations. He repeatedly stresses the “impossibility” of AA and CC being simultaneously true. His language goes beyond merely noting the falsity of certain compound propositions; rather, it indicates that, under the given conditions, configurations such as:

T	F
F	T

are logically untenable.

All three valid configurations maintain the core propositional opposition relations: contradiction ($AA \leftrightarrow BB \vee CC \leftrightarrow DD$), subalternation ($CC \rightarrow BB \vee AA \rightarrow DD$), contrariety ($AA \uparrow CC$) and subcontrariety ($BB \vee DD$). By conjoining these tautological relations, we obtain a generalized version of formula (1) that structurally characterizes Table 1:

$$(AA \leftrightarrow BB) \wedge (CC \leftrightarrow DD) \wedge (CC \rightarrow BB) \wedge (AA \rightarrow DD) \wedge (AA \uparrow CC) \wedge (BB \vee DD)$$

In this reduced truth table: AaB corresponds to AA , AoB to BB , AeB to CC , and AiB to DD .

Shortly after the examined passage, Aristotle reaffirms that these oppositional relations fully apply to categorical propositions (*Prior Analytics* I.46, 52a18–24). Specifically, he demonstrates that: “*Not all things are white*” (BB) does not constitute the negation of “*All things are non-white*” (CC), and “*Every animal is non-white*” (CC) is

not the negation of “*Every animal is white*” (AA). When analyzing these relations through Table 2, we observe that the categorical propositions AaB , AoB , $\bar{A}aB$, and $\bar{A}oB$ respectively exhibit oppositional patterns identical those of the metalinguistic propositions AA , BB , CC , and DD :

$$(AaB \leftrightarrow AoB) \wedge (\bar{A}aB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}oB) \wedge (\bar{A}aB \rightarrow AoB) \wedge (AaB \rightarrow \bar{A}oB) \wedge (AaB \uparrow \bar{A}aB) \wedge (AoB \vee \bar{A}oB)$$

This same schema remains invariant when considering the converse forms BaA , BoA , $\bar{B}aA$, and $\bar{B}oA$ in the same order, confirming the consistency of Aristotle’s system:

$$(BaA \leftrightarrow BoA) \wedge (\bar{B}aA \leftrightarrow \bar{B}oA) \wedge (\bar{B}aA \rightarrow BoA) \wedge (BaA \rightarrow \bar{B}oA) \wedge (BaA \uparrow \bar{B}aA) \wedge (BoA \vee \bar{B}oA)$$

What Aristotle does not explicitly state is that some metalinguistic letters represent defined propositions (true under only one truth-value configuration), while others represent undefined propositions (true under two non-equivalent truth-value configurations). In the original structural formula, the affirmative propositions AA and CC are defined (true exclusively in the first and third configurations respectively). Their contradictories, the negative propositions BB and DD , are undefined (true in two distinct configurations: BB in the second and third, DD in the first and second). Aristotle’s analysis implicitly treats the contradictory of an indefinite proposition as definite (*Topics* III.6).

In the concluding section of Chapter 46, Aristotle presents an equivalent reformulation of the same logical structure. He reorganizes the square of opposition such that AA becomes an undefined proposition while BB becomes defined—reversing their initial configuration:

[...] Without qualification, whenever A is so related to B that it is not possible for them to belong to the same thing at the same time but of necessity one or the other of them belongs to everything [$AA \leftrightarrow BB$], and C and D, in turn, are likewise related [$CC \leftrightarrow DD$], and A follows C and does not convert with it [$CC \rightarrow AA$], then D will follow B and will not convert with it [$BB \rightarrow DD$]. Also, it is possible for A and D to belong to the same thing [$AA \vee DD$] but not possible for B and C [$BB \uparrow CC$]. (*Prior Analytics* I.46, 52a39–52b4)

The oppositional relations remain valid. However, by redefining AA as undefined and BB as its defined contradictory, the logical connections yield an alternative reformulation of the basic structural formula:

$$(AA \leftrightarrow BB) \wedge (CC \leftrightarrow DD) \wedge (CC \rightarrow AA) \wedge (BB \rightarrow DD) \wedge (BB \uparrow CC) \wedge (AA \vee DD)$$

The only truth-value combinations consistent with this scheme are:

1. ^a	T	F	2. ^a	F	T	3. ^a	T	F
	T	F		T	F		F	T

This configuration clearly shows that AA and DD are undefined propositions (true under two non-equivalent configurations), while BB and CC are defined propositions (true under only one configuration each).

When applied to the propositions in Table 1, this logically equivalent version of the original structural formula reproduces formula (1) exactly. Similarly, its implementation

on the categorical propositions of Table 2 (after proper relabeling) produces no changes. In all cases, we observe the possibility of alternative propositional reassignments through systematic exchange of defined and undefined propositions. Furthermore, any proposition can be substituted by its logical equivalent without compromising the system's consistency.

8. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that reduced truth tables—when properly adapted to Aristotelian logic by excluding empty terms and strictly observing traditional oppositional relations (contrariety, subcontrariety, contradiction, and subalternation)—provide rigorous verification of the system's tautologies when incorporating negated terms.

We have comprehensively systematized the system's basic logical equivalences, revealing their fundamental structural principle: symmetry under term complementation. Each equivalence (e.g., $AaB \leftrightarrow \bar{A}eB$ through obversion) generates a complementary version ($\bar{A}a\bar{B} \leftrightarrow Ae\bar{B}$) obtained by uniformly replacing all terms with their complements.

The introduction of equivalence classes with negated terms that were not considered in traditional syllogistic theory does not affect the validity of established syllogisms. Instead, it provides a more comprehensive model of the underlying semantic scenarios. Furthermore, we demonstrate that Aristotelian syntactic reductions can be semantically validated using truth tables.

Closure under complementation not only ensures that Aristotelian logic maintains its consistency when handling negated terms but also establishes a formal basis for interpreting key passages like *Prior Analytics* I.46—where Aristotle discusses negated terms—without requiring *ad hoc* rules.

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